

Fab25 Czechia – Bridge the Gap. Fab25 Research Papers Stream

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Abstract

FAB25 Czechia is the 2025 edition of the FABx event – the flagship gathering for FabLabs, makers, innovators, researchers, educators, and artists. This year, the event is united under the theme “Bridge the Gap.” The Fab 25 research papers stream includes original scholarly writing from researchers studying the Fab Lab movement, its ambitions and its impact from a wide range of disciplines, including computer science, engineering, science and technology studies, business and management, education, urban studies, media and design, and many more.

Keywords

Fab Lab, Impact, Education, Experiments

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1 Translocal impact

1.1 Measuring the Impacts of Fab Labs: A Review of Quantitative Research and Evidence

Jan Peuckert, Victoria Wenzelmann and Gerrit Rüdibusch

This review addresses a critical gap in academic research by systematically assessing the quantified societal impacts of Fab Labs. Recognizing the need for rigorous evidence to inform policy, funding, and strategic planning, it focuses on studies employing robust quantitative methodologies. Using the Fab City Full Stack as a framework, the review categorizes findings across seven interconnected layers, from local production technologies to global knowledge sharing. It evaluates measurable economic, educational, environmental, and social outcomes, emphasizing metrics derived from econometric models, longitudinal studies, and statistical analyses. By examining prior research methodologies, this study highlights the transformative potential of Fab Labs in fostering sustainable localized production, community empowerment, and educational innovation. The synthesis of empirical evidence provides actionable insights for stakeholders seeking to design evidence-driven interventions. Ultimately, this review strengthens the evidence base for Fab Labs' societal impact, supporting cities in their transition toward regenerative and inclusive ecosystems.

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1.2 Blueprint for Urban Manufacturing – An Exploratory Multi-Dimensional Canvas

Matteo Subet, Serena Cangiano, Enrico Bassi and Desirée Veschetti

The term Urban Manufacturing (UM) is used to refer to the production of goods within urban areas using locally sourced materials, with the resulting products being released in the same location. Factories that adhere to these principles are known as Urban factories. Within the project LAUDS Factories – a research initiative focused on establishing guidelines for scaling up production in urban areas that embody the principles of Local, Accessible, Urban, Digital and Sustainable manufacturing – a co-creation approach has been explored focusing on the development of experimental urban productions that are both compliant with fundamental UM concepts and advanced LAUDS principles. This co-creation approach in designing future production infrastructures and models is significant; therefore, a specific framework has been designed and tested to comprehensively document how the experimental initiatives are set up and developed. The paper presents the work in progress on the design of a documentation tool called LAUDS Blueprint which has been designed, prototyped and tested as an initial step towards detailing the processes involved within LAUDS-centric factories, elucidating their objectives through the identification of challenges, proposed solutions, accumulated knowledge, and potential business opportunities. The aim of this paper is to offer insights into the development process of this LAUDS Blueprint through an iterative approach, alongside two real-case applications.

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1.3 Open-Source Software and Open-Source Hardware under the new European Product Liability Directive

Tarmio Emanuel, Sathya Frei and Greta Sparzynski

As part of the European Green Deal, the EU aims to become fully climate-neutral, promoting sustainable innovation through a circular economy. Open-Source Software and Open-Source Hardware play a key role in this transition, enabling repairable, durable, and collaboratively designed products. However, despite their potential to contribute significantly to EU sustainability goals, many open-source developers remain hesitant to publish or commercialize their work due to legal uncertainties and liability risks. These “chilling effects” stem primarily from concerns over strict liability for defects under the existing EU Product Liability Directive (Directive 85/374/EEC). In response, the EU has adopted a revised Product Liability Directive (Directive (EU) 2024/2853) to modernize liability rules for the digital age. Notably, it explicitly excludes free and open-source software developed outside commercial contexts from strict liability and clarifies rules for digital manufacturing files and software. This article examines whether the PLD New provides the legal certainty necessary to reduce liability fears and unlock the full sustainability potential of Open-Source Software and Hardware. It introduces the concepts, stakeholders, and previous legal challenges, before analysing the directive's impact and critically assessing whether it represents a turning point or a new obstacle for the open-source movement in Europe.

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2 Education

2.1 Developing a Co-Creation Makerspaces on Renewable Energy Technology for Children: Multi-Stakeholder Insights on Challenges and Solutions

Christian Stadlmann and Andrea Holzinger

Purpose: This paper investigates the challenges and solutions in developing a co-creation makerspace initiative for children, focused on renewable energy technology.

Methodology/data: A comprehensive methodological approach was employed, combining case study analysis, reflection reports, and qualitative semi-structured interviews with 4 trainers and 4 key stakeholders involved in the initiative. Above, the study utilized the analytical framework provided by Mersand (2021).

Findings: The study identified several challenges, including pedagogical aspects, financial sustainability, workshop development, parental involvement, organizational issues, social and diversity barriers, and safety concerns. These challenges varied depending on the format of the sub-initiatives: permanent maker groups, school workshops, and summer events.

Research implications: The findings suggest that addressing these challenges requires tailored strategies for different formats, such as enhanced financial planning, improved communication, and inclusive practices. A list of potential countermeasures is provided. Further research should explore larger, diverse samples, comparative studies in various geographical settings, and longitudinal studies assessing long-term impacts.

Original value: This study contributes by providing insights into the case-specific challenges and solutions, highlighting the importance of context-related strategies, and elaborating differences to previous studies and novel elements. These insights may help other initiatives address common problems and enhance their effectiveness with the proposed solution approaches.

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2.2 Emerging opportunities for digital fabrication education. The making of the ‘Caparazón de madera’ pavilion

Ronan Bolaños, Brandon Velazquez and Marcos Ontiveros

The purpose of this paper is to report on how we integrated a method for manufacturing double curvature surfaces with cold-pressed wooden parts, and how this research and educational experience developed in the form of a pavilion. During the process, we set some goals, reducing costs from previous experiences, with further intricate geometry, configuring an agile assembly and disassembly for the parts, developing an efficient and safe structure, making a visually attractive and apparent simple geometry, with a natural and renewable carbon sequestrant material. We built with enthusiastic participants in a curricular workshop, where they acquired their first or most important experience and significant knowledge in computational design and digital fabrication throughout the making.

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2.3 The network beyond the network: the potential of FabLabs as partners in participatory environmental monitoring efforts

Óscar González Fernández and Rebecca Anne Peters

This speculative paper analyses the theoretical potential for FabLabs to take part in participatory environmental monitoring efforts using open technologies on a large scale and contribute to reporting networks in Europe. It explores where FabLabs could fit into the European environmental monitoring ecosystem, while considering their role as often situated at the crossroads between various stakeholder groups, and presenting potential venues of collaboration between FabLabs and traditional actors within environmental monitoring. The argumentation for this paper leverages the multifaceted role of FabLabs, positing that they can provide access to infrastructure, training, skills and beyond, and therefore have the potential to play a pivotal role in participatory environmental monitoring efforts as a network, ultimately acting as an agent that enables both, long-term sustainable engagement, and large scale data collection. This potential is explored through analysis of experiential data in the provision of low-cost environmental monitoring devices and the support to beneficiaries from a Fablab perspective, which is complemented with existing data regarding FabLabs’ skill sets and manufacturing capabilities; interests, motivations, and current activities; and finally, their location in relation to points of interest specific to environmental monitoring

that enhance this potential. Taken together, this analysis seeks to consider the scalability of participatory environmental monitoring activities within the FabLab network itself, through multi-stakeholder collaboration between traditional actors and FabLabs, the potential impact of such partnerships, and suggestions for next steps.

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3 Local experiments

3.1 Embodied Knowledge in Digital Spaces: Towards Human-Centered Fabrication Formats

Jorge Muñoz Zanón

This research investigates the preservation of embodied knowledge and creative agency within digital fabrication processes and contexts. The historical division between conception and execution, intensified by industrialization, has been perpetuated in digital formats that prioritize geometric precision over tacit knowledge. While neo-craftspeople have adapted digital tools to their practices, current representation systems fail to capture the essence of making that characterizes craft processes. Through an experimental multi-modal computer vision pipeline implemented with pottery artisans, this study develops the .crtf format, a time-based representation that preserves not just what was created, but how it emerged through hand movements, material interactions, and decision-making processes. By drawing from cross-cultural preservation models that prioritize adaptation over static conservation, this research proposes alternative digital fabrication paradigms that honor rather than erase the human dimensions of making. The findings suggest that true democratization of fabrication requires reimagining not just access to tools, but the fundamental relationship between maker, material, and technology in ways that reunite conception with execution and preserve the maker's voice throughout the creative process.

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3.2 Hyperlocal Bio-Hygienic Technologies

Tomas Vivanco

The centralized production of personal hygiene products ensures standardization and effectiveness for various consumer needs. However, these processes heavily rely on petroleum-based components and significant water content, contributing to global environmental challenges such as climate change. Additionally, when distributed as universal solutions, these products often fail to adapt to local habits, resources, and cultural practices. This study employs a Research through Design (RtD) methodology to explore sustainable, hyperlocal alternatives to mass-produced hygiene products. By leveraging indigenous production techniques and locally sourced biomaterials from four distinct Chilean bioregions, this research proposes a decentralized model for personal hygiene product development that considers local materials, heritage and communities, aligning with ecological and cultural sustainability.

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3.3 Opportunities and considerations for flexible electronics fabrication using a vinyl cutter

Jessica Stanley

Fablabs have had a major impact on the accessibility of electronics fabrication, alongside innovation in the broader maker movement such as Arduino and Raspberry Pi. From designing and milling custom printed circuit boards, to combining electronics and fabrics to make e-textiles, electronics fabrication is no longer restricted to professionally trained electronic engineers or highly skilled hobbyists. There is, however, a category of electronic device that has yet to see widespread uptake the fablab community: flexible electronics. Rather than describing any electronic circuit that is flexible, flexible electronics normally refers to circuits made from conductive tracks on flexible polymer films, either with or without components. Although flexible electronics manufacturing is an established industry, with applications ranging from e-textiles to soft robotics, there are relatively few documented flexible electronics projects from fablabs. This paper gives an overview of flexible electronics fabrication inside and outside fablabs, and explores potential methods for fablab-based fabrication using a vinyl cutter. Two flexible PCB fabrication methods are presented, and compared to standard techniques. Flexible circuit boards with features as small as 100 μm are demonstrated, along with practical considerations to be taken into account for high quality results, and discussion of needs for future work to properly validate the methods in collaboration with the fablab community.

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3.4 The Algorithmic Thobe: A Parametric Exploration of Jordanian Heritage Through 3D Printing

Batoul al-Rashdan

This paper explores the intersection of computational couture and traditional Jordanian craftsmanship, emphasizing parametric design and 3D printing as innovative approaches to heritage preservation. Jordanian cross-stitch embroidery, deeply embedded in regional identity, artisanal practices, and socio-cultural narratives, faces increasing threats from globalization and mass-produced fashion. By proposing a digital reinterpretation of these embroidery techniques through advanced computational methods, this study seeks to maintain cultural authenticity and traditional aesthetics while enhancing garment functionality, personalization, and sustainability. Utilizing software tools such as Rhinoceros and Grasshopper, traditional embroidery patterns are algorithmically translated into parametric designs, producing customizable, scalable, and modular textile forms via digital fabrication technologies. This approach not only safeguards endangered cultural practices but also addresses contemporary fashion challenges by merging digital heritage preservation with innovative textile methodologies. The paper positions itself within the broader scholarly contexts of computational fashion and digital heritage preservation, addressing critical concerns such as cultural appropriation and providing practical insights for sustainable and culturally respectful fashion innovations.

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4 Preprints

Preprints are not peer-reviewed.

4.1 Knowledge dynamics and makerspaces: proximities and local development in the Central Europe

Lukas Danko, Grzegorz Micek and Karolina Kapustka

The rationale behind this working paper is reflected in the investigation of knowledge partners and the role of proximities through makerspaces. Hence, these spaces are creating a positive impact on creating a cultural change by encouraging entrepreneurship in the community, support small business growth, and increase workforce retention. Therefore, the focus is on the knowledge partners and the local growth, in the selected Central European countries (Poland, Czechia, Slovakia), where makerspaces have seen a more significant increase. Furthermore, the paper aims to shed some light on both direct and indirect effects of makerspaces on local development. The research design is based on empirical qualitative analysis of primary data gathered through semi-structured interviews with stakeholders in makerspaces. The novelty of our empirical research is reflected in identifying spatial scales to distinguish the role of proximity in knowledge transfer through makerspaces. The working paper presents policy implications to nurture different knowledge flows in and its role in local development. Furthermore, the research reflects on the knowledge transmission among the central knowledge partners considering different proximities.

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4.2 Flexible Fabrication-Driven Design Approach for Product Development in Fab Labs

Georgi Chervendinev and Emilia Ochkova-Dimitrova

This paper examines a flexible, fabrication-driven design methodology in Fab Labs, highlighting how digital fabrication tools enable customizable, scalable product development. It explores the benefits, challenges, and implications of this approach in modern manufacturing.

Design/Methodology/Approach: A practice-based methodology is used to analyse modular product systems with adjustable connections for applications such as furniture, stage sets, and automotive tuning. The study integrates theoretical discussions on digital fabrication with practical insights from case studies and prototyping experiments.

Data/Sample: The research evaluates design iterations, fabrication test results, and user feedback from Fab Lab environments to assess flexibility, efficiency, and adaptability.

Findings: A fabrication-driven approach enhances adaptability, reduces material waste, and optimises customization. Modular and parametric design strategies improve digital fabrication efficiency, making them ideal for small-scale manufacturing and prototyping. This approach proves effective across multiple domains.

Research Limitations/Implications: Scalability may be limited by specific digital fabrication tools. Future research could explore large-scale applications and long-term product durability.

Practical Implications: Integrating fabrication-driven principles into Fab Lab workflows improves prototyping, efficiency, and innovation, supporting cost-effective and sustainable product development.

Originality/Value: This study offers insights into digital fabrication and flexible design, benefiting Fab Lab practitioners, industrial designers, and engineers optimising customisation and production efficiency.

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4.3 From Memory to 3D Prototype: Constructing the Collective Memory of the Cultural Center “La Carmela” Puebla, Mexico

David Valdez

This study explores the construction of the collective memory of the "La Carmela" Cultural Center in Puebla, Mexico, a space historically stigmatized by violence and abandonment. Through an action-research methodology, the project "Let's desembrujar El Castillo" was developed, which developed literary stories with augmented reality (AR) created by young people from the area, based on the testimonies of five residents over 20 years old in the area. The objective was to activate processes of symbolic resignification of the place and strengthen the sense of community belonging. The findings reveal that AR, when appropriated from a critical pedagogical perspective, can become an emancipatory tool that allows excluded communities to narrate their history and dignify their spaces. The tensions between memory, oblivion and urban exclusion are reflected in the ambivalent perception of the site: a place loaded with affection, but also with stigma. Experience suggests that emerging technologies, integrated into participatory educational processes, can contribute to subjective and collective transformation. The original value of the study lies in articulating technologies, political action and community narratives as a strategy for heritage recovery and the creation of meaningful links in marginalized urban contexts.

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4.4 Comparative Analysis of Standard and Casting Resins in mSLA 3D Printing for Precision Lost Wax Casting Applications

Michał Burza

This study investigates the integration of modern 3D printing technologies with traditional precision casting methods, specifically exploring the application of mSLA (masked Stereolithography) printing as an alternative to conventional wax model preparation in the lost wax casting process. Two types of UV-curable resins—standard and wax-like casting resin—were comparatively evaluated for dimensional accuracy, surface quality, and casting defects. Models were printed using an Elegoo Mars 2 printer, converted to metal castings via the lost wax method, and subjected to comprehensive dimensional analysis using 3D scanning and GOM Inspect software. Results demonstrate that 3D printed models maintain high dimensional accuracy regardless of their placement on the printing platform, with deviations generally within ± 0.1 mm. The casting resin models yielded superior castings with fewer defects compared to standard resin, which left ash residue during burnout causing porosity and underfilling issues. While the higher cost of specialized casting resins presents a limitation, their performance advantages make the mSLA printing technique particularly suitable for small-batch production and complex geometries in jewelry making and precision engineering applications where traditional manufacturing methods prove challenging.

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